

Logic Gates Based on Synthetic Antiferromagnetic Bilayer Skyrmions

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Technologies based on magnetic skyrmions such as novel computational devices that can operate at high speed or low energy consumption have been proposed by many researchers. Recently, synthetic antiferromagnetic (SyAF) structures have been proposed to increase the stability and mobility of skyrmions by reducing or eliminating the skyrmion Hall effect. Here, we numerically study the current-induced dynamics of skyrmions on SyAF bilayer structures. We demonstrate the effective control and manipulation of SyAF skyrmions, including the directional displacement and alignment. Besides, we design SyAF skyrmion-based logic gates such as the AND, OR, XOR and NOT gates. Our design provides guidance for future development of spintronic computing devices that use topological nanoscale spin textures as information carriers.

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I. Introduction

Magnetic skyrmion is one of the most useful magnetic spin textures, which shows non-trivial topology. The existence of skyrmions in magnets was predicted by Bogdanov et al. in 1989 [1] and the magnetic skyrmions were observed experimentally for the first time in 2009 [2]. By virtue of their high potential in future spintronic applications, magnetic skyrmions have aroused a particular interest in the spintronics community [3-9]. A number of theoretical and experimental works have shown that skyrmions can exist in different types of ferromagnetic systems, including bulk materials [10-12], thin films [14-16], and multilayers [17-24].

The promising feature of magnetic skyrmions is they can be used to build the next-generation of information storage and logic computing devices [25-27]. Nanoscale skyrmions carrying binary information can be displaced in thin films and nanotracks driven by a moderate electric current [28], which is an effective way for information transmission [29]. For example, the magnetic skyrmion-based racetrack memory is an advanced information storage device [30] proposed based on the conventional domain-wall-based racetrack memory [31], where magnetic skyrmions move in ferromagnetic nanotracks driven by spin-polarized current. However, several obstacles, such as the skyrmion Hall Effect (SkHE), are encountered in the way to make skyrmion-based in-line motion devices reliable and practically commercialized [32-34]. For example, the SkHE may result in the undesired destruction of skyrmions at the edges of the skyrmion-based racetrack memory structure [35]. Therefore, great efforts are deployed to solve problems related to the realization of skyrmion-based devices [36], leading to more complex and prospective designs such as the racetrack memory based on synthetic antiferromagnetic (SyAF) skyrmions [37-39]. Another appealing non-volatile information storage device is the skyrmion-based magnetic random-access memory (MRAM) [40-41], which are mainly based on the manipulation of magnetic skyrmions in spin valve structures [42-43]. Since the first experimental observation of skyrmions, the field has also focused on the skyrmion-based conventional logic computing devices [44-46] and novel computing strategies [47, 48].

In this work, we computationally demonstrate the skyrmion-based logic computing by utilizing the current-driven skyrmion motion and skyrmion-skyrmion interactions in a SyAF bilayer structure. The studied system is a ferromagnet / spacer / ferromagnet trilayer, where the two ferromagnetic (FM) layers are strictly exchange-coupled in an antiferromagnetic (AFM) configuration [49]. In such a SyAF structure, the SkHE of a bilayer skyrmion can be totally suppressed [36].

II. Simulation

A. Simulation methods

We simulate the SyAF skyrmion-based logic computing operations by using the open-source micromagnetic simulator MuMax3 [50], where the magnetization dynamics is controlled by the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert (LLG) equation augmented with spin-orbit torques (SOTs) or spin transfer torques [51].

For the skyrmion dynamics driven by SOTs, we consider a current-perpendicular-to-plane (CPP) geometry, and the LLG equation with the damping-like SOT term read [52, 53]

$$\frac{d\mathbf{m}}{dt} = -\gamma\mathbf{m} \times \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}} + \alpha \left(\mathbf{m} \times \frac{d\mathbf{m}}{dt} \right) - \frac{\hbar\theta_{\text{SH}}J}{2meM_S t_{\text{FM}}} \mathbf{m} \times (\mathbf{m} \times \boldsymbol{\sigma}) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{m} = \frac{\mathbf{M}}{M_S}$ is the normalized magnetization and $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \overline{u}_y$ in our model. The effective field is the functional derivative of system functional energy

$$\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}} = -\frac{1}{\mu_0 M_S} \frac{\delta E_{\text{tot}}}{\delta \mathbf{m}} \quad (2)$$

In this work, the total average energy density E_{tot} includes both intra and interlayer exchange couplings, Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction (DMI), perpendicular magnetic anisotropy (PMA), and demagnetization terms, see supplemental file for further information about the theoretical formwork [54,79,80,81]. The material parameters are given as those of Co/Pt systems with spin Hall angle -0.33 degree, Exchange stiffness $A_{\text{intra}} = 15 \text{ pJ m}^{-1}$, interlayer exchange coupling constant $J_{\text{inter}} = 6 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}$, Gilbert damping coefficient $\alpha = 0.3$, saturation magnetization $M_S = 580 \text{ kA m}^{-1}$, PMA constant $K = 0.8 \text{ MJ m}^{-3}$, and iDMI strength

$D = 3.5 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}$. To balance the accuracy and efficiency, all models are discretized into tetragonal elements with the size of $2 \text{ nm} \times 2 \text{ nm} \times 2 \text{ nm}$. The effect of DMI on the structure total energy and skyrmion size is discussed in Supplemental Material Fig. S1 [54].

B. Design of SyAF bilayer structures

As illustrated in Fig. 1a, the simulated model is composed by two FM layers separated by a metallic spacer in order to guarantee the existence of an AFM interlayer exchange coupling, which plays a key role to suppress the SkHE.

In this work, skyrmions are driven by using SOTs. The CPP current is injected in the heavy metal substrate and the spin current is present in the bottom FM layer [55]. The interlayer exchange coupling in this situation drives the skyrmion in the top FM layer. The electric current distributions in the heavy metal are simulated using COMSOL Multiphysics [56], and the profiles found are applied to micromagnetic simulation to examine the reliability of our designed logic gates. The experimental realization of our logic gates is discussed in section IV.B.

III. Skyrmion dynamics on SyAF bilayer structure

We first study the skyrmion dynamics on SyAF bilayer structures when the out of plane current is applied. As known different current disposition can serve to induce skyrmion dynamics. The two methods widely used are the STT consisting on a current flowing inside the ferromagnetic layer and the SOT based on a current flowing in a heavy metal substrate. Recently, several studies have found discrepancy skyrmion dynamic between experimental result and analytical results based on the Thiele model, where interfacial STT has significant effect on the ultrathin structure with small skyrmion [57, 58]. The combination of the interfacial STT and the SOT results in a smaller skyrmion Hall angles in experiment. However, in SyAF structure, the

skyrmion hall effect are exactly cancelled due to the coupling between skyrmions on the top FM layer and the bottom FM layer. Therefore, the interfacial STT is not considered in this work.

In our study, we used SOT driving method to move magnetic skyrmion in the SyAF structure. Different current densities were applied to induce SOT to drive skyrmions on both ends to move towards the center, as shown in Fig. 2. At a driving current density of 50 MA cm^{-2} , skyrmions move towards the center and stabilize at 4.5 ns. To understand the trajectory of the skyrmion, we consider forces that contribute to the motion and pinning of skyrmion. Previous studies reported several important forces that are present when skyrmions are moving on nanotracks [59, 60], including skyrmion-skyrmion repulsion, the Magnus forces (related to the SkHE), the skyrmion-edge repulsion, and the driving force. For our SyAF structure, only the skyrmion-skyrmion repulsion, Skyrmion-edge repulsion and the driving force resulting from SOT are considered.

The stabilization of the skyrmions at the center when we apply a current density of 50 MA cm^{-2} can be understood as the interplay between the driving force and the repulsion force between skyrmions after they collide with each other. In this situation, the driving force is not strong enough to overtake the skyrmion-skyrmion repulsion and leads skyrmions to get closer.

The speed of the skyrmion increases and the spacing between skyrmions decreases as we enhance the current density applied on the structure. The increase of current density induces greater driving force, hence reducing spacing between skyrmions. The spacing between two skyrmions after collision (at the simulation end when the skyrmion pair is reaching an equilibrium under driving forces compensation) with respect to the current density applied are shown in Fig. 3. In the first portion of the curve, the spacing between two skyrmions decreases as the current density applied increases. It reaches minimum when current density equals 100 MA cm^{-2} .

When the applied current density is larger than 100 MA cm^{-2} , further increase of current density rise the spacing between skyrmions until 200 MA cm^{-2} , as demonstrated in Fig. 3. This increase of spacing can be related to the skyrmion size and the trajectory changes, as shown in Fig. 2 and the inset b of Fig. 3. It is noticed

that the skyrmion size reduces as the current density increases, which may be due to the act of compression force contributed by the driving force and skyrmion-skyrmion repulsion. In addition, we can see the motion changes as the skyrmions reach the center. Instead of stabilizing in the same horizon, both skyrmions start moving in the vertical direction. This movement is seen after the shrink of the skyrmions size, which gives skyrmions more space and direction to move on the narrow nanotrack. As a result, an angle between the driving force and the skyrmion-skyrmion repulsion force is created. Thus, the vertical component of the skyrmion-skyrmion repulsion force repels the skyrmions vertically, creating more spaces between them. The increase of spacing stops when the skyrmions are aligned vertically in the center.

Further increase in current density will cause the skyrmion pair to rotate by an angle of 90 degrees and align vertically at the center, as shown in Fig. 2a (500 MA cm^{-2}). The result is consistent with Fig. 3, where the distances between skyrmions barely changed with respect to the increase of current density magnitude after 200 MA cm^{-2} . This trajectory changes show that the driving force induced by the current density is competing with the repulsive force between two skyrmions.

Based on the above-studied dynamical properties of skyrmions, we have successfully induced motion, and alignment of skyrmions on SyAF bilayer structures. Thus, with these basic operations, we are able to design efficient elementary logic gates, including the AND, OR, XOR and NOT gates. Recently, many devices based on skyrmion have been proposed [61-62]. It is believed that skyrmion-based computing devices are promising as they have advantages of low energy consumption and can operate at extreme high speed [63-70]. The design of logic gates proposed in this work is summarized in Fig. 1.

IV. SyAF skyrmion-based logic gates

A. Proof of concept

1. OR logic gate

The logical OR gate is constructed on three-terminal SyAF bilayer structures as illustrated in Fig. 1d. Input A and Input B are located on the left and the right ends of the structure. The Output is located in the center of the structure. In skyrmionics logic, the presence of a skyrmion represents logical 1 and the FM ground state represents the logical 0. The logical OR gate is operated such that $0 + 0 = 0$, $1 + 0 = 1$, $0 + 1 = 1$ and $1 + 1 = 1$. We demonstrate the operation of the OR gate in Fig. 4. The process of $0 + 0 = 0$ is trivial, meaning that there is no skyrmion on the Input and the Output. The process of $1 + 0 = 1$ is interpreted as follows. When a skyrmion is present in Input A and no skyrmion in Input B, only one skyrmion will travel to the Output, representing the logical 1 (Fig. 4 Left Panel). Similarly, the process $0 + 1 = 1$ is interpreted by the presence of a skyrmion in Input B and the absence of a skyrmion in Input A. The skyrmion will travel to the center, representing the logical 1 in the output (Fig. 4 Middle Panel). The most important process $1 + 1 = 1$ is interpreted by the presence of skyrmions on both Input A and Input B. Two skyrmions align themselves vertically in the center (Fig. 4 Right Panel). The repulsion force interacts between the vertically aligned skyrmions, and push one of them into the protruded area, which represents the logical 1 in the Output.

2. AND logic gate

The SyAF bilayer AND logic gate is designed with a similar structure as the OR gate. Different from the OR gate, the detection area (Output) is at the protruded area next to the center of the SyAF structure as shown in Fig. 1c. In skyrmionics logic, the presence of a skyrmion represents logical 1 and the ferromagnetic ground state represents the logical 0. The logical AND gate is operated such that $0 + 0 = 0$, $1 + 0 = 0$, $0 + 1 = 0$ and $1 + 1 = 1$. During operation, out-of-plane currents applied on both sides, inducing SOT to push the skyrmion moving towards the center. We demonstrate the operation of the AND gate in Fig. 5. The process of $0 + 0 = 0$ is trivial, meaning that there is no skyrmion on Input and Output. The processes of $1 + 0 = 0$ and $0 + 1 = 0$ are similar to the OR gate, where a skyrmion is present on either Input A or Input B to represent the logical 1 and ground state on the other Input to represent the logical 0. However, since the Output is no longer in the

center, the skyrmion stabilized in the center will not enter the protruded area next to it. Thus, no skyrmion can reach the Output, thus represents the logical 0 (Fig. 5 Left Panel and Middle Panel). The most important operation $1 + 1 = 1$ is interpreted by the presence of skyrmions on both Input A and Input B. Two skyrmions will meet each other's and align themselves vertically in the center. The repulsion force interacts between the vertically aligned skyrmions, and push one of them into the protruded area, which represents the logical 1 in the Output (Fig. 5 Right Panel).

3. XOR logic gate

The SyAF bilayer XOR logic gate is designed with a similar structure as the OR gate. Different from the OR gate, the detection area (Output) is at the center area of the track, with two protruded area next to it, as shown in Fig. 1c. In skyrmionics logic, the presence of a skyrmion denotes logical 1 and the ferromagnetic ground state represents the logical 0. The logical XOR gate is operated such that $0 + 0 = 0$, $1 + 0 = 1$, $0 + 1 = 1$ and $1 + 1 = 0$. During operation, out-of-plane currents are applied on both sides, inducing a SOT force to push the skyrmion moving towards the center. We demonstrate the operation of the XOR gate in Fig. 6. Similarly to OR gate, the process of $0 + 0 = 0$ is trivial, meaning that there is no skyrmion on the Input and the Output entities. The processes of $1 + 0 = 1$ and $0 + 1 = 1$ are similar to the OR gate, where a skyrmion is present on either Input A or Input B to symbolize the logical 1 and ground state on the other Input to signify the logical 0. The skyrmions will stabilize in the Output area located in the center, representing the Output logical 1 (Fig. 6 Left and Middle Panel). The most important operation $1 + 1 = 0$ is interpreted by the presence of skyrmions on both Input A and Input B. Two skyrmions will meet each other in center. Similarly to the AND gate, two skyrmions will align vertically in the center, and due to the repulsive interaction, they will push one another away from the Output area in the center. The lack of the skyrmion in Output represents the logical 0 (Fig. 6 Right Panel).

4. NOT logic gate

For the NOT logic gate, the concept is different. We try to drive the skyrmion along two crossed nanotracks. The Input region is located on the start of each nanotracks and the output is at the end. (See Fig.1.d). The presence of a skyrmion on the first track Input region represent logical 1 and the presence of skyrmion on the second track Input region represent logical 0. For the NOT gate operation, we have $1 = 0$ and $0 = 1$. As shown in Fig. 8a, for the case $1 = 0$, it is interpreted by placing a skyrmion in the input region on the first nanotrack. An out-of-plane current will be applied to drive the skyrmion towards the end. The absent of skyrmion in the Output region of the first nanotrack and the it's presence in the Output region of the second nanotrack represents the logical 0 in the output (Fig. 7 Left Panel). For the case $0 = 1$, it is interpreted by placing a skyrmion in the input region on the second nanotrack. An out-of-plane current will be applied to drive the skyrmion towards the end. The presence of skyrmion in the Output region of the first nanotrack and it's absence in the Output region of the second nanotrack represents the logical 1 in the output (Fig. 7. Right Panel).

B. Logic gates with realistic current values

Now we study the feasibility of realizing the proposed skyrmion logic gates based on synthetic antiferromagnets. In our design, the skyrmion logic computation is executed by controlling the skyrmion trajectory, which is induced by the electric currents flowing toward the center. Therefore, the grounding of the system may alter the electric current when the grounding contact is small. We investigate this issue with electric current simulation using the electrical module of COMSOL Multi-physics [56], where different grounding sizes are applied to understand their influences on current distribution on the heavy metal substrate, as shown in Fig. 8. Since our micromagnetic simulations were carried out using Co/Pt multilayers parameters, we simulate in COMSOL a Pt layer with an electrical conductivity $\sigma = 9.43 \times 10^6$ S/m, a resistivity of $\rho = 1.06 \times 10^{-7} \Omega/m$ and a relative permittivity $\epsilon_1 = 0.7347$, $\epsilon_2 = 2.7604$. These current distribution profiles

are applied to the micromagnetic simulation, where we find that the logical computation of the OR, AND and XOR gate can be achieved with grounding size 40 nm or above.

On the other hand, the previous results are carried out with the material parameters presented in section II. Currently, experiments on Pt/Co multilayer thin films suggests that the Gilbert's damping coefficient on such system is lower [71-74]. Therefore, recent studies on skyrmion logic gates are usually conducted with $\alpha = 0.1$ [44, 75]. We apply these finding on our design and find that the current density required in our system are greatly reduced to 50 MA/cm².

As demonstrated in Fig. 9.a-9.c, the critical operation 1+1 of the three gates are realized by applying current density of 50 MA/cm², which is lower than the current density 100 MA/cm² or 300 MA/cm² used in previous experimental works on SyAF structures [76, 77]. Besides, we also took in consideration the effect of the electric ground on the current created on our system by applying the current profiles from COMSOL simulations. As a result, our gates were valid for systems with a $\delta_{Ground} = 40$ nm as exposed in Fig. 9.c. Additionally, the required current density for the operation of AND, OR and NOT gates can be further decrease to 30 MA/ cm² when these skyrmion based logic gates are realized on CoFeB as shown in Fig.9.d [29].

Our findings demonstrate that the electric current required to execute logical operation varies in materials with different damping coefficient α . Thus, we perform micromagnetic simulation analysis to study skyrmion motions on the three system (CoFeB, Co/Pt with $\alpha = 0.1$ and Co/Pt with $\alpha = 0.3$) with different applied electric current density. It is obvious that the skyrmion velocity are significantly enhanced in CoFeB and Co/Pt with $\alpha = 0.1$ systems when compare with the skyrmion velocity on Co/Pt with $\alpha = 0.3$ under the same electric current density. The enhancement of velocity by the reduction of damping coefficient of the materials can be explained by the skyrmion motion in Thiel's framework as given by [78]:

$$\vec{G}_{Sk} \times \vec{v} + \alpha \vec{D}_{Sk} \vec{v} = \vec{F}_d \quad (3)$$

Where \vec{v} is the skyrmion velocity, \vec{G}_{Sk} is the gyro-vector, \vec{D}_{Sk} is the dispation tensor and \vec{F}_d is the driving force due to the spin Hall effect. In SyAF structure, the gyro-vector is reduce to zero, as described by [36], and the dispation tensor \vec{D}_{Sk} could be expressed using a 2x2 matrix $\vec{D}_{Sk} = \begin{pmatrix} D & 0 \\ 0 & D \end{pmatrix}$. Therefore, Eq. 3 can be deduced to $v = \frac{F_d}{\alpha D}$, where the skyrmion velocity is inversely proportional to the damping coefficient α . As a result, in materials with lower damping coefficient α , the same skyrmion motion can be obtained with lower current density, as demonstrate in fig.9.

V. Conclusions

Skyrmion-based techniques provide promising routes to fabricate computational devices that can operate in high speed or low energy consumption. In this work, we analyze the dynamics of skyrmions on SyAF bilayer structures at different current density, where the current is applied in opposite direction. Our result indicated that using electrical current, the skyrmions interaction and the skyrmion-edge repulsion we could align and rotate skyrmions in SyAF bilayer structures. With these findings, we are able to design elementary logic gates that are essential for skyrmion based computation devices. Hence, we report the designed and simulation result of OR, NOT, AND and XOR logic gates that are built on SyAF bilayer structures. Our results provide information for designing computation magnetic devices that use topological nanoscale spin textures as information carriers. Moreover, our results will help to design future magnetic devices and spintronic devices.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

FIG. 1. Schematic illustrations of our simulated SyAF structures with a length of 500 nm and a width of 100 nm. The thickness of each ferromagnetic layer was fixed in 2 nm (a) ZX cut of our SyAF bilayer used for OR logic gate; (b) OR / AND logic gate schematization; (c) XOR logic gate schematization; (d) NOT logic gate schematization. I_{nucl} denotes the skyrmion writing current and I_{read} denotes the reading current.

FIG. 2. Dynamics of skyrmions in a SyAF bilayer nanotrack driven by the SOT at different current densities. The spin current was injected on the bottom ferromagnetic layer coming from the heavy metal substrate.

FIG. 3. Spacing between two skyrmions at the final state as a function of the current density applied to the system. Current density is applied ranging from 10 to 400 MA/cm². The spacing is measured once the skyrmions are stabilized after collision.

FIG.4. Logical OR operation based on SyAF bilayer skyrmions. The skyrmion represents logical 1 and the ferromagnetic ground state represent the logical 0. The logical OR gate is constructed on three-terminal SyAF bilayer structures with 500 MA/cm² working current. The Input A and Input B (Red square) are two ends of the SyAF bilayer structures while the Output detection is made in the central area in the center (Green square).

FIG. 5. Logical AND operation based on SyAF bilayer skyrmions. The skyrmion represents logical 1 and the ferromagnetic ground state represent the logical 0. The logical AND gate is constructed on three-terminal SyAF bilayer structures with 500 MA/cm² working current. The Input A and Input B (Red square) are two ends of the SyAF bilayer structures while the Output detection is made in the protruded area in the center (Green square).

FIG.6. Logical XOR operation based on SyAF bilayer skyrmions. The skyrmion represents logical 1 and the ferromagnetic ground state represent the logical 0. The logical XOR gate is constructed on three-terminal SyAF bilayer structures with 500 MA/cm² working current as illustrate in Fig. 1c. The Input A and Input B (Red square) are two ends of the SyAF bilayer structures while the Output detection is made in the protruded area in the center (Green square).

FIG. 7. Logical NOT operation based on SyAF bilayer skyrmions. The logical NOT gate is constructed by a cross structure made of SyAF bilayer track with 300 MA/cm² working current as shown in Fig. 1.d.

Fig.8: Current distribution inside a heavy metal (Pt) layer. a) Sketch of the simulated device; b) The longitudinal current component along the system length for three different sizes of the electric ground; c) the three spatial current components for $\delta_{\text{Ground}} = 40 \text{ nm}$. The inset show a zoom on the grounded part for the three components of the electric current density.

Fig.9: SyAF Skyrmion OR, AND, XOR logic gates succeeded in Co/Pt and CoFeB with different electric ground lengths. a) Logic gates implemented in Co/Pt with $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\delta_{Ground} = 20$ nm ; b) Logic gates implemented in Co/Pt with $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\delta_{Ground} = 30$ nm; c) Logic gates implemented in Co/Pt with $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\delta_{Ground} = 40$ nm; d) OR, AND logic gates implemented in CoFeB/HM with $\alpha = 0.015$. We present in the figure only the 1-1 operations since the 1-0, 0-1 and 0-0 are easy to succeed at low current values.

Fig.10: SyAF Skyrmion speed versus current for three different systems. The green and red curves show the skyrmion velocity evolution versus current for Co/Pt with the material parameters listed in section two of the manuscript and $\alpha = 0.3$ and $\alpha = 0.1$ respectively. The black curve show the skyrmion velocity versus current for CoFeB with material parameters as follow: $A_{intra} = 20$ pJ m⁻¹, $\alpha = 0.015$, $M_s = 1$ kA m⁻¹, $K_u = 0.8$ MJ m⁻³, $D = 1.8$ mJ m⁻² and $J_{inter} = -8$ mJ m⁻².

FIGURES

Figure. 1

$J(\text{MA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2})$	50	200	500
SOT Skyrmion motion	0 ns 		
	2 ns 		
	4.5 ns 		

Figure. 2

Figure. 3

OR Gate					
Input A	Input B	Input A	Input B	Input A	Input B
1	0	0	1	1	1
t= 0 ns	t= 0 ns	t= 0 ns	t= 0 ns	t= 0 ns	t= 0 ns
t= 0.4 ns	t= 0.4 ns	t= 0.4 ns	t= 0.4 ns	t= 1 ns	t= 1 ns
1	1	1	1	1	1
Output	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output

Figure. 4

AND Gate					
Input A	Input B	Input A	Input B	Input A	Input B
1	0	0	1	1	1
	t= 0 ns	t= 0 ns	t= 0 ns		
	t= 0.4 ns	t= 0.4 ns	t= 1 ns		
0	0	0	1	1	1
Output	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output

Figure. 5

XOR Gate					
Input A	Input B	Input A	Input B	Input A	Input B
1	0	0	1	1	1
<p>t= 0 ns</p>					
<p>t= 1.8 ns</p>					
1		1		0	
Output		Output		Output	

Figure. 6

NOT Gate SOT	
Input	Input
1	0
<p>t= 0 ns</p>	
<p>t=2 ns</p>	
0	1
Output	Output

Figure. 7

Figure. 8

Figure. 9

Figure. 10